

Object perception through visual attention

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Abstract Dynamic and robust visual perception is made possible through active vision, which offers an alternative to the conventional feedforward architectures in computer vision, these are typically static and passive, relying heavily on large datasets and substantial computational resources. When learning to recognise new objects, infants actively explore their environment through coordinated sensorimotor interactions, guided by feedback that shapes perception [1]. The integration of Sensorimotor Contingencies Theory (SMCT) with active vision is effectively demonstrated in the work of Maye et al. [2], where sensorimotor sequences are used to learn object representations within a visual scene. However, most vision datasets either (i) rely on static, 2D frame-based input that fails to capture the embodied, sensorimotor nature of real-world object interaction, while also demanding high computational resources and large amounts of data, or (ii) consist of 3D datasets that, although they represent more realistic geometries, typically lack mechanisms for identifying attentional regions of interest (ROIs) or simulating fixational eye movements. Furthermore, existing pipelines seldom integrate all components essential for autonomous robotic perception, including continuous gaze shifts, event-based sensing, and saliency-driven object exploration. To address these gaps, we develop a bioinspired, event-based attentional architecture, building upon the work of D'Angelo et al. [3], that emulates visual exploration by shifting the focus of attention through object motion sensitivity. This mechanism mimics overt selective attention and enables efficient filtering of visual input, allowing the system to focus computational resources on the most informative regions of the scene [3, 4]. Expanding on this foundation, we incorporate sensorimotor sequences for object learning and propose a four-stage process: (i) simulation of micro-saccadic fixations on synthetic 3D-modeled objects; (ii) conversion of rendered video into event streams; (iii) computation of dynamic saliency maps to extract attentional regions of interest (ROIs); and (iv) generation of spatial saccadic trajectories.

Methods We use the Objaverse-XL dataset [5] and the Sketchfab plugin integrated with Blender to render high-quality videos of 3D objects under simulated micro-saccadic movements, modelled as a Gaussian random walk ($\sigma_{\text{pan}} = 0.1^\circ$, $\sigma_{\text{tilt}} = 0.09^\circ$) on the camera's local pan and tilt axes. The camera is first oriented to fixate the object before the pan and tilt jitter begin. Using the IEBCS simulator, our rendered videos are converted into an event stream. This stream is then processed by an event-driven saliency-based bioinspired visual attention mechanism, which, through temporal filtering, generates dynamic saliency maps. Thus, our ROIs are defined as the most salient locations over time (t), and saccades (s_t) are computed as the vector displacement between consecutive attentional shifts, represented as $s_t = \{\Delta x_t, \Delta y_t\}$.

Results and discussion We implemented a pipeline that transforms 3D visual stimuli into event-based saliency representations, producing sequences of ROIs and corresponding saccadic movements. This system enables the continuous ex-

Figure 1: SMCT pipeline. *a)* An example of a frame from the synthetic video (720×480 px) of a tea cup. *b)* An example of an event frame of accumulated DVS events capturing temporal light changes in the scene. *c)* Sequence of saccadic shifts $\{(\Delta x_t, \Delta y_t)\}$ calculated from the visual attention architecture. *d)* Extracted regions of interest (ROIs) – each covering 10% of the original frame area – around each attentional fixation, highlighting the most informative elements of the scene.

traction of sensorimotor contingencies over time, effectively encoding the spatial structure of rigid bodies into temporal dynamics. It lays the groundwork for future work in contrastive learning, where this attentional data will be used to train spiking neural networks via biologically inspired contrastive mechanisms, enabling efficient and robust object categorisation grounded in sensorimotor integration.

References

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